

JAVASCRIPT TILIDA O'ZGARUVCHILAR

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Anotatsiya: Ushbu tezisdan JavaScript dasturlash tilida o'zgaruvchilarni e'lon qilishning usullari, o'zgaruvchilarni nomlash qoidalari va o'zgaruvchilar qamrovi (scope) haqida ma'lumot beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: JavaScript, o'zgaruvchi, var, let, const, scope.

Аннотация: В данной диссертации представлена информация о методах объявления переменных в языке программирования JavaScript, правилах именования переменных и области видимости переменных.

Ключевые слова: JavaScript, переменная, var, let, const, область видимости.

Abstract: This thesis provides information on the methods of declaring variables in the JavaScript programming language, the rules for naming variables, and the scope of variables.

Keywords: JavaScript, variable, var, let, const, scope.

JavaScript tilida o'zgaruvchilar - bu ma'lumotlarni saqlash uchun konteynerlar (ma'lumotlar qiymatlarini saqlash). JavaScriptda o'zgaruvchilarni e'lon qilishning 4 xil usuli bor bo'lib quyidagilar kiradi: var, let, const va hech narsa ishlatmasdan.

O'zgaruvchilar - bu ma'lumotlarni saqlash uchun konteynerlar (ma'lumotlar qiymatlarini saqlash). Ushbu misolda, **x**, **y** va **z**, o'zgaruvchilar bo'lib, ular **var** kalit so'z bilan e'lon qilinadi:

```
var x = 5;
var y = 6;
var z = x + y;
```

Ushbu misolni let kalit so'zi bilan e'lon qilishga misol keltiramiz.

```
let x = 5;
let y = 6;
let z = x + y;
```

Ushbu misolda, **x**, **y** va **z**, e'lon qilinmagan o'zgaruvchilar:

```
x = 5;
y = 6;
z = x + y;
```

O'zgaruvchilarni e'lon qilish uchun var, let va const kalit so'zlari ishlatiladi. var kalit so'zi 1995 yildan 2015 yilgacha barcha JavaScript kodlarida qo'llaniladi. let va const kalit so'zlari 2015 yildan boshlab JavaScript kodlarida qo'llaniladi. Agar siz eski browser ishlatsangiz u holda var kalit so'zidan foydalanishingiz zarur bo'ladi. const kalit so'zi bilan e'lon qilingan o'zgaruvchi o'zgartirib bo'lmaydi. Misol uchun PI ni qiymati o'zgarimas bo'lib uni const bilan e'lon qilishimiz mumkin. O'zgaruvchi nomlari harflar (A-Z va a-z), raqamlar (0-9), pastki chiziq (_) va dollar belgisi (\$) dan iborat bo'lishi mumkin. O'zgaruvchi nomlari raqam bilan boshlanmasligi kerak. O'zgaruvchi nomlari JavaScriptda maxsus ma'noga ega bo'lgan kalit so'zlardan foydalanib bo'lmasligi kerak. O'zgaruvchi nomlari katta-kichik harflarga sezgir. O'zgaruvchi nomlari ma'noli va tushunarli bo'lmasligi kerak. O'zgaruvchilar qamrovi

(scope) bu o'sha o'zgaruvchining ko'rinish nuqtasi va o'sha nuqtada unga murojaat etish imkoniyatini anglatadi. JavaScriptda ikkita turi scope bor: global scope va local scope. Global scope da e'lon qilingan o'zgaruvchi kodning har qaysi joyidan ko'rinishi mumkin va murojaat etish mumkin. Local scope da e'lon qilingan o'zgaruvchi faqatgina shu scope ichida ko'rinishi mumkin va murojaat etish mumkin. Local scope da function scope va block scope ga ajratiladi. Function scope da e'lon qilingan o'zgaruvchi faqatgina shu funksiya ichida ko'rinishi mumkin va murojaat etish mumkin. Block scope da e'lon qilingan o'zgaruvchi faqatgina shu blok ichida ko'rinishi mumkin va murojaat etish mumkin. Blok bu {} orasidagi kod hisoblanadi. var kalit so'zi bilan e'lon qilingan o'zgaruvchi function scope ga tobe bo'ladi. let va const kalit so'zlari bilan e'lon qilingan o'zgaruvchi block scope ga tobe bo'ladi.

Xulosa:

Ushbu tezisda JavaScript dasturlash tilida o'zgaruvchilar mavzuini tahlil qildik. Biz o'rganib chiqdik ki, JavaScriptda o'zgaruvchilar nima, ularni nomlash qoidalari nima va ularning turli xil scopelari nima. Biz shuningdek, var, let va const kalit so'zlari orqali o'zgaruvchilar bilan ishlashni ham ko'rib chiqdik.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

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